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USING SCHEMATA AS A COGNITIVE DESIGN PROCESS: A CASE STUDY OF DRAWN COGNITIVE MAPS AND ENVIRONMENTAL PERCEPTIONS AND EXPECTATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This study addressed and evaluated the statistical results and relationships between: (a) The amount of travel experience a person has and the impact of this experience to upcoming travel experiences, and (b) Identified the objects and events one indicated as a significant element - however defined by the participant - within the airport terminal. Significant results from the study showed events after the travel experience, identified as POSTceptions, (based upon a projected and drawn mental maps of specific environmental spaces, utilizing schemata from projected mental maps and previous, although not always similar, user experiences) were greater in frequency and significance than those who anticipated specific events prior to the travel experience, identified as PREceptions (similar to POSTception, but based on anticipated events that could occur within the space). These experiences, especially those significant in nature include: circulation paths, wayfinding signage, indication and location of restrooms and lines/queues, and airport employees.

Keywords: Interior design, cognitive mapping, perceptual schemata.

INTRODUCTION

This study addresses the relationship between affordances of the built environment and the associations between PREception and POSTception cognitive maps, especially those involving one's anticipation, movement, and actual behavior in airports. The airport environment provides a solid, structured foundation of specific and orderly events through

which a person progresses; although wayfinding and circulation through an airport is identifiable, people still have numerous opportunities to get off track (Edwards, 2005). While similar research has begun to investigate similar recalled experiences through airports and wayfinding (Raubal, Egenhofer, Pfoser, & Tryfona, 1997), there is no existing research utilizing perceptual schemata, drawn cognitive maps indicating specific cognitive maps, and using content analysis to identify specific elements that are anticipated, experienced, and recalled. Thus, the aim of this study is to develop a new methodology and case study to evaluate environmental perceptions within the built environment.

ENVIRONMENTAL PERCEPTIONS AND POSTCEPTIONS

An Environmental PREception is the concept based upon a projected mental map of a specific environmental space. It utilizes expectations or beliefs concerning future experiences based upon projected mental maps and previous, although not always similar, user experiences. The foundation of PREceptions asks the subjects fundamental questions such as: "What should you expect to be in the space?" "What will be in the space?" and "What could potentially be in the space?" (Gentry, 2010a, 2010b). Actual Experience, for the case of this study, was defined as the time when one was in a specific environment recording one's cognitive map and the significant spaces of the built environment. There was no need for a projection or recall of the experience, as the subject was still within the space recording their thoughts and memories. Environmental POSTception, similar to the PREception concept, is based upon a recalled mental map of a specific environmental space after a specific period of time has passed since the user has

been within the specific space. It utilizes the information from the environmental PREception and the Actual Experience to recall a space, frequently using the stored mental maps and recalled significant elements of the space. The foundation of POSTceptions asks the subjects fundamental questions such as “What did you expect to be in the space?”, “What do you recall as significant elements of the space you are asked to recall?”, and “How did you know how to function within this particular space?”

BACKGROUND

IMAGE SCHEMATA

Bartlett (1932) introduces the concept of schemata as internalized images that represent an active organization of past experiences that is used to structure and interpret future events. Johnson (1987) further proposes a recurring pattern which is grounded in people’s experience. This pattern assists subjects to organize and structure space while allowing them to be able to know what to do with the experience. Lawson (2006) identifies the role of cognitive psychology and its influence in the design process. Psychologists Raubal, Engenhofer, Pfoser, and Tryfona (1997) apply Johnson’s image schemata concepts into alternative conceptualizations and cognitive models of space, built upon people’s experiences for a particular environment, such as an airport through the use of sequential photography. Raubal et al indicate image-schemata correlate with other image schemata in the form of image-schemata blocks, which rarely occur in isolation, and function as knowledge-representation schemata for wayfinding tasks. Arnheim (1983) describes architecture as temporal constructs formed out of complete perceptual images and believes the viewer becomes an active part of architecture, and appearances are altered as a result of particular sequence. In contrast, Heft and Wohlwill (1987) contend that Arnheim’s two views are not mutually exclusive, as environmental conditions (contextual factors) and personal goals may ultimately determine whether perceptual or cognitive processes are required:

Wayfinding can be directly related to previous experience through the same space or by comparing the experience to other similar environments.

ROUTE-LEARNING MECHANISMS

Psychologists Siegel and White (1975) identify mechanisms used to foster and facilitate the learning of predetermined routes. Route-learning can be learned through one’s conventional sensorimotor system. Although the authors are not in the position of providing a formal analysis of what this specific system is, it is likely possible to identify elements or characteristics of what the system must contain: a route must involve a sequence of decisions—generally, changes in direction; and knowledge of a route conceivably exists through a type of serial learning—a memorized series of decisions as established through repetition of the route.

COGNITIVE MAPPING

Characteristics of cognitive maps are based, in part, from a person’s previous experiences and prior learning (Evans & Pezdek, 1980; Presson & Hazelrigg, 1984; Thorndyke & Hayes-Roth, 1982). Knowledge of spatial layout is acquired through the direct observation of the environment or through navigation (Presson & Hazelrigg, 1984). Cognitive maps tend to become similar to cartographic maps when an environment becomes more familiar (Evans, Marrero, & Butler, 1981; Gärling, Böök, & Engezen, 1982); this happens early in the acquisition process if the environment is more limited. Further ideation of cognitive map formation introduce the way in which people come to think about their world, and how it is affected by their exposure to representations of their world and not only from direct physical experience (Liben, 1991).

Lynch and Rivkin (1959) conclude that a person must perceive their environment as an ordered pattern and constantly interject order into it, so that all relevant perceptions are cohesive. Subsequent applications and uses of the environment reinforce the perceptive cohesion. Lynch and Rivkin acknowledge habitual use and perception allow the subject to unify the subject’s perceptions of the environment. Accuracy increases with the amount of previous experience (Evans, et al., 1981; Gärling, et al., 1982); there are possibly also qualitative changes

in cognitive maps as a function of previous experience.

COGNITIVE MAP AS A HYBRID OF SPATIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL COGNITION

Although spatial cognition and environmental cognition are similar terminology, it is pertinent these terms be identified and explained further. Hart and Moore identify “spatial cognition” as the knowledge and internal or cognitive representations of structure, entities, and relations of space (1973). Cohen (1985) identifies “place cognition” as a union of spatial knowledge, social knowledge, and an understanding of the physical and social nature of environments. Place cognition, further defined by Hart and Conn (1991) brings closer to meaning and action in a place as the focus of human intentions. Consequently, the study of place leads to the simultaneous investigation of thinking, feeling, and acting in the environment.

COGNITIVE TRAVEL PLANS

Kuipers (1978) and Siegel and White (1975) assume that a path previously traversed is shown in cognitive maps as an ordered subset of places. There are many ongoing action plans that people carry out, only a few of which are related to travel plans. Consequently, other things may be learned about an environment without the intended purpose being to facilitate the travel. Aesthetic qualities, symbolic meanings, and atmosphere are among those things represented in cognitive maps of environments that have immediate functional significance. These actions do contribute to future experiences within the space since they act as memory aids (Harrison & Howard, 1972; Merrill & Baird, 1980; Stokols, 1981; Stokols & Shumaker, 1981). The main function of cognitive maps focus on the facilitation of movement and travel in the environment (Gärling, Böök, & Lindberg, 1984). Once an environment becomes familiar, it is likely that places are easily recognizable and that the number of known places (reference points) increases to the point where it is almost superfluous for a person to monitor their location (Gärling, et al., 1984). Travelers’ observations consist of a sequence of sensory and motor descriptions: views and actions (Kuipers, 1982). Navigational strategies are classified in terms

of the demands they place on memory storage and cognitive processing, independent of their implementation in a particular agent (Foo, Warren, Duchon, & Tarr, 2005).

COGNITIVE MAPS AND EXPERIENCE

Mental spaces, also considered cognitive maps, are not internalized images of external space; rather, they are schematized, through elimination of detail and simplification of features. They are mental constructions built around frameworks consisting of elements and relationships based upon their specific location and proximity (Tversky, Morrison, Franklin, & Bryant, 1999). Cognitive maps are schematized too, yet they differ in significant ways from mental representations of space. The space of experienced navigation is often learned vicariously from maps and descriptions, as well as actual experience. Utilizing elements such as landmarks, paths, cities, countries, and reference frames (such as surrounding geographic entities or north, south, east, west) facilitate how a person patches the separate segments together (Tversky, et al., 1999).

DRAWING FROM EXPERIENCE

Lynch (1960) theorizes that individuals who were more familiar with an urban space concentrated on specific landmarks for navigational purposes more than on paths. Appleyard (1970, 1976) supports Lynch’s arguments and stated their maps were dominated by sequences of events and greater path usage. Devlin (1976) additionally supports that newcomers to an area focused on the same pathways, show a greater increase in landmark identification, indicating that initial paths are based upon initial structures through continuous exposure. Downing (2003) addresses the connection between memories and places. Gathering together “image banks” through the process of drawing identify the “how and why” a place is important and acknowledges that each person’s image is unique, recurring patterns begin to emerge. Memories are symbolic summation and elaborations of our unique experiences; Downing (2003) believes that these memories provide mental imagery in the mind and identifies the mapping of one object on to different domains as a product of people’s discursive form of reasoning.

Creating a schema of a particular experience and drawing the actual experience is not based on an abstract philosophical construction, but on human experience and in order to discover and understand new ideas, or new concepts, Black (1962) states that one needs to utilize metaphoric references to bring two separate domains into cognitive and emotional relation through language or imagery. Understanding no experience is never exactly repeated, Downing (2003) further identifies the use of past knowledge to frame present or future situations as demanding abstraction, adjustment, and evolution of ideas.

METHODOLOGY

PREception/POSTception Methodology

This study uses (a) drawn cognitive maps based on anticipated and predicted experiences, actual experiences, and recalled experiences; and (b) amounts of experience participants have had within similar built environments. Utilizing drawn cognitive maps to indicate significant elements along the participant's journey allow for both qualitative and quantitative results to indicate significant recalled elements as participants travel through the specific environment, for this study, the Des Moines International Airport.

This study collected one demographic and informational survey and three hand-drawn cognitive maps (drawn expectations or recollections of environmental experience) drawn by the participants. The first survey, identified from this point forward as the "PREception", was conducted two weeks prior to departure to collect anticipated expectations of the journey through the Des Moines International Airport. Participants also completed a survey to collect demographic information and to establish the amount of travel experience. At this time, participants finally drew a map of their expected journey through the Des Moines International Airport, from entry into the building until boarding the aircraft. The second phase, identified from this point forward as the "Actual Experience", was conducted on the actual day of the travel experience, shortly after completing the journey through the airport. The participants were asked to draw a second map, which was collected two weeks after the PREception map, which

consisted of their route through the airport, while they were still in the airport terminal, and to annotate any significant spatial experiences they encountered. The final phase, identified as the "POSTception", was two weeks after the participants' departure (Actual Experience) from the Des Moines International Airport. A final map was again drawn and used to compare the recalled and significant experiences of the participants' journey through the departing airport.

A content analysis of the significant spaces from the surveys and drawn maps were done to determine correlative relationships and significances between frequency of travel and PREceptions, Actual, and POSTception experiences. The content of the maps were reviewed and lists of potential categories were generated to conduct content analysis. Two methods of analysis, conceptual analysis and relational analysis, were considered to evaluate the text and concepts. The investigator adopted the relational analysis methodology to evaluate the data. The duration of this particular was approximately one month and consisted of three phases: The PREception phase, which was two-weeks prior to the travel experience; the Actual Experience, on the day of the travel experience prior to boarding the aircraft; and the POSTception phase, two-weeks after the travel experience. The dates for this study were September 2, September 16, and September 30, 2009, respectively.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data were analyzed using descriptive, correlative, and categorical statistics, including, one-way ANOVA and bivariate correlative statistics. The significance level used in this study was $p = .05$ (Hinkle, Wiersma, & Jurs, 2003). The analyses evaluated the differences between the three specific times the maps were drawn (PREception, Actual Experience, and POSTception; i.e.: experience) and between levels of travel experience, as identified by the participant from the information provided on the demographic survey (Figure 1). Four subject groups were created based upon the frequency of participant travel (either domestic or international) within the past five years. These groups are identified as: Never Travel, Infrequent Traveler,

Subject group	Amount of travel within 5 years	Number of subjects (n)
Never Travel	0 times	3 subjects

Moderate Traveler, and Frequent Traveler.

Figure 1. Matrix of Groups based upon frequency of travel

TREATMENTS AND CONTROLS

This study focused on a hybrid of experimental and observational approaches was used to create the design of the study. The intention was to maintain control over as many aspects of the environment as possible (e.g.: select a specific event and site for the event to be recorded). However, the nature of observational studies allowed the participants to control what information was indicated on the cognitive maps, and was therefore not controlled by the researcher. The researcher requested that participants partake an identical experience: all events would be experienced at identical times and conditions. This would allow for maximum control of variables within the study.

Firstly, since all subjects were tested in exactly the same conditions, and under exactly the same experimental conditions, the result cannot be automatically assumed to apply to other locations and environments. Secondly, the fact that the baseline and experimental conditions were always carried out in the same order will almost certainly have been a contributing factor within the study, i.e.: there will have been a learning effect from the first time the participants completed the survey to the second time, given that the questions were exactly the same. Finally, there is no way the researcher can be sure that some other confounding variable was not responsible for the result, since there was no experimental control in the overall process.

CASE STUDY

CASE STUDY HYPOTHESES

Numerous hypotheses for content and statistical analysis within this study were asked:

In terms of cognitive maps of pedestrian airport experience (including such considerations as interior qualities, spatial qualities, perception of the physical environment, etc.), what are the linkages between what people think will occur within the airport environment and what actually occurs? How do these

differ between individuals with different amounts of travel experience?

2. What specific events and landmarks are stored in a cognitive map as one navigates through an unknown space?
3. In which way do PREceptions, Actual Experience, and POSTceptions factor into the cognitive maps of people who have more travel experience compared to those who don't frequently travel?
4. How can cognitive maps, PREceptions, and POSTceptions provide useful information (e.g.: interior qualities, spatial qualities, perception of the physical environment) to designers of interior environments?

CASE STUDY OVERVIEW

The crux of this survey addresses and evaluates the statistical results and relationships between (a) the amount of travel experience a person has and the impact of this experience to upcoming travel experiences, and (b) identifies objects and events one indicates as a significant element - however defined by the participant - within the airport terminal.

The participants in this study were undergraduate students ($n=17$) in the interior design program at a Midwestern as they participated on an international field study to Toronto, Canada. The specific interior environment was regional airport, the excursion origin. Although a limitation was the participant group consisted of interior design students, assumptions were made that participants would focus and indicate interior elements on the drawn cognitive maps in their PREception, actual experience, and POSTception. A major finding was not the indication of interior elements, but indication of circulation, wayfinding elements, and individuals and employees who could answer specific questions within in the airport environment.

CASE STUDY OUTCOMES

DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

The analyses evaluated the differences between the three specific times the maps were drawn (PREception, actual experience, and POSTception) and between the four different levels of travel experience, as identified by the participant from the

information provided on the demographic survey (Figure 1).

Figure 2 identifies the categories as having significant statistical relationships between the compared categories, using the ANOVA test between travel experiences (i.e.: PREceptions, Actual Experiences, and POSTceptions) ($p= .05$); subject groups ($p= .05$); and significant correlational relationships between the three travel experiences ($p= .05$).

Figure 2. Comparison of similar significant categories

SUMMARY OF CASE STUDY AND CONCLUSIONS

The ANOVA significant categories ($p= .05$) based on experience are: check-in, baggage, gates, signage, previous experience, to follow/following, entrance, and lines/queues. The ANOVA significant categories ($p= .05$) based on subject group are: to wait/waiting, retail, restrooms, parking, seating, terminal, employees, arrivals, play area. The correlative relationships based upon experience are: to wait, restrooms, seating, employees, previous experience, arrivals, play area, and lines/queues (Figure 2). Significant results from the study showed that events after the travel experience, identified as POSTceptions, indicated an increased frequency on participant’s drawn cognitive maps compared to the drawn cognitive maps of anticipated specific events prior to the travel experience, identified as a PREceptions. These experiences, especially those significant in nature were based on the circulation paths, or getting from one specific point of origin to a specific, defined destination.

IMPLICATIONS

The findings from this study revealed that the users of a particular environment, especially the structured and procedural-driven environment of the airport, the contributing factors within the PREceptive/Actual Experience/POSTceptive were not driven by architectural or interior elements, but driven by factors that contribute to circulation through the space (e.g.: signage, following, and previous experience). The data from this exploratory study also indicated that majority of the significant elements noted on the subject’s cognitive maps were in the “non-sterile” or public environment of the airport terminal, rather than the “sterile”, post-security environment. This implies that although the procedural cues may be known and present, such as knowing where to enter the terminal and the process of checking in at the front ticket counter, may be known. However, opportunities are present where people must make a decision and become confused and disoriented.

Secondly, this study indicated a significant difference between the identification of signage and other methods of circulatory guidance. A greater emphasis must be placed on directional signage and environmental graphics within the interior design programming phase. This repeated emphasis of circulation and wayfinding indicates that even though interior environments may be familiar even to frequent travelers, the elements of signage and signs are still noted and expected to assist in circulation guidance.

Finally, a factor that is usually not considered in the design process, the stagnant areas where lines/queues and waiting occurs, was significantly noted by the participants. Although these areas can frequently occur spontaneously and sporadically, the participant groups across all levels of travel experience indicated this as a significant (neither positive nor negative significance measured) element of the airport terminal.

LIMITATIONS

The purpose of this study was to compare the relationships between cognitive maps and the physical interior environment of the airport. This study examined the linkages between what people thought would occur within the airport environments

and what actually occurs and how these indications differ, in particular, between individuals with different amounts of travel experience. In other words, do the specific events, objects, and landmarks vary from projected, actual, or recalled experiences? How do these events, objects, and landmarks vary based upon people's amount of travel experiences? The issues listed below were identified as possible limitations of this study.

First, the participant group was extremely small ($n = 17$), so the amount of data analyzed and coded was very small. This created difficulty in creating categories and maintaining a substantial amount of responses to run specific statistical analyses, (such as a Chi-Square statistical test or other predictive statistics) could not be run due to the relatively small sample size and level of responses. Further opportunities would lie in creating broader categories that would allow the investigator the ability to either focus on a more narrow range of categorical analyses (having more categories, but create sub-categories which could be expanded or contracted as needed) or strictly focusing on specific types of events, objects or activities.

The identical methodologies and procedures could be applied to a larger group, perhaps utilizing a larger population, to compare and refine the hypotheses assumed from this study. The small sample size of this study could then function as a pilot test to which more specific questions could be asked to drive the coding and data to receive a much more rich, developed, and diverse outcome.

Secondly, while this particular study was fortunate to utilize subjects who were taking the same exact trip for an academic course, the demographic criteria was extremely specific: the age of the subjects was within four years, the gender of the subjects were identical, the academic field of study was identical and design related, and the subjects all had known one another and developed relationships which extended beyond the academic boundaries into a casual and informal nature. While this provided an excellent group of participants who understood the principles and theories of interior design, it may have provided a bias as to what types of information was indicated on the mental maps, as well as how the mental map was physically drawn.

Third, the results of this study were tailored to a specific airport terminal; the investigator would not consider the data collected from this experiment to be all encompassing for all airport terminal environments, regardless of size, function, and location of airport terminals. Additionally, the organization and layout of the Des Moines International Airport is very simple compared to larger airports, such as O'Hare International Airport in Chicago, IL and Hartsfield-Jackson Atlanta International Airport in Atlanta, GA. Further studies using similar, if not identical, methodologies and procedures could be used in other transportation, hospitality, retail, or institutional environments. Finally, the only interaction the investigator had with the participants was during the PREception and POSTception phases, during the administration of the survey and maps. It may have been more effective to conduct one on one interviews with the participants, especially those who identified as never traveling before or frequent travelers, then transcribe and code the interviews to create additional qualitative and quantitative data to be analyzed.

FUTURE RESEARCH

Recommendations for Future Research

Based upon the research findings and experiences from this study, the following recommendations are suggested for future research:

Use other groups of design professionals, or non-designers. Instead of focusing on the profession of the participant group, consider using a hybrid of design professionals, such as architecture, graphic design, or urban planners. All of the subjects, if identifying as any formal description of "designer" might provide a subliminal bias towards elements in their perspective professional field. Additional studies, consisting of participant groups of designers, non-designers, or the public would allow for further depth and exploration of correlative relationships and identification of events and landmarks. These two groups could be compared using the same methodology and procedure utilized in this study. Use PREceptions and POSTceptions as an evaluative instrument. The interior design profession uses a Post Occupancy Evaluation (POE) to revisit a newly designed or renovated space to observe the

occupants function within the space and to consider making minor changes to the observed space or note major programmatic changes to make when considering the design of similar spaces in the future. The PREception and POSTception methodology could become part of the designer's programmatic interview process and POE evaluation process.

Use other aspects of the terminal experience. This study concentrated on the circulation and landmarks from the entry into the terminal until boarding the aircraft. A future study evaluating how a person understood the process of making a connecting flight or the disembarkation process from the airline to exiting the building, would provide another opportunity to compare the events and the order one perceives or encounters these objects.

Evaluate drawing style of the cognitive maps. Analyze how the participant actually drew the map (i.e.: Is the map drawn in a floor plan view or perspective? Was the sheet orientation in landscape or portrait layout? Which elements would one include/exclude based upon the size of the paper to draw the map? Were people drawn in the map? How did the participant indicate circulation?) What would provide additional insight on the perception and interpretation of the space to be evaluated? Comparisons between designers and non-designers could create benchmark between what is understood and intended by the designer and what is understood and perceived by the non-designer.

CONCLUSIONS

PREception/POSTception Methodology

The PREception/Actual Experience/POSTception methodology utilized in this study allows for numerous opportunities within the context of interior design. The methodology can be utilized within the programmatic phase of a design project. As part of the programming and research procedures, interviews can be conducted with users of the space. For example, when working on the program for a commercial office space, one-on-one interviews of the occupants can include a drawn cognitive map of how they anticipate the space to function. Within this drawn cognitive map, the designer can collect both qualitative and quantitative data to assist the

designer to identify the specific needs of the user. By utilizing this specific user group, one can classify them as the "experienced user", comparing them to the frequent travelers indicated in this study. Further interviews can be conducted with users who have some interaction with the space (e.g.: corporate managers who visit the space, but do not inhabit the space on a full-time basis), and could compare to the Moderate travelers of this study. Interviews could then be conducted with individuals who rarely visit the space, such as guests who might visit the space once a year, and would be similar to the Infrequent or Never travel groups.

Post Occupancy Evaluation using PREception/POSTception Methodology

Using the same participants from the programmatic phase identified above, a POSTception map could be drawn, using the same methodology as the PREception map. Making a comparison between the PREception and POSTception drawn cognitive maps and the indicated significant spaces would provide quantitative data that could support Post Occupancy Evaluations (POE), which would be conducted by the designer after the installation had been complete and the users had occupied the space for a short period of time.

The information collected from the drawn cognitive maps and an additional interview process could identify specific needs that are lacking within a space, as well as excessive. From this study, there was indication that participants were expecting more directions to aid them with circulation throughout the airport terminal. When there was missing signage, participants might indicate "I didn't know where to go" and this would provide a cue that some form of direction is necessary at this specific point in the circulation path. Because this was specifically indicated on a drawn cognitive map of an identifiable space, the designer could return to the approximate area to experience themselves what the conditions might have been at the time that the participant had asked that question. This is particularly true if it were indicated on the Actual Experience drawn cognitive map, as the participant was still physically within the environment. The information from this methodology not only provides information based upon the amount of

experience of the participant, but through the PREception/Actual Experience/POSTception procedures, information would be collected as to what elements or events created memories from the space.

Role of Employees in the Specific Environment

Further conclusions observed from this study indicated the participants identified employees within the terminal. Although no specific employees were referenced, other than those at the Homeland Security/TSA security check, their identification by the participants indicates the presence of the employees is observed by the traveler, even if only a passive indication. This also creates an opportunity for the designer to educate and interview the airport employee as a user group.

The airport employee might provide a different drawn cognitive map compared to the traveler. Due to the nature of the airport terminal and its layers of security zones, the airport employee might not always provide the most efficient and direct path when asked for directions by a lost passenger, because the employee might have different circulation paths than the traveler, and these paths, because they are not specifically within the public spectrum, might not have adequate signage to facilitate circulation. Therefore, the airport employee might have to retain numerous and more detailed cognitive maps than the traveler, and the landmarks the employee could identify to the lost traveler might not be the same landmarks as the traveler within the airport terminal.

Role of Environmental Graphic Design

Key elements identified in this study, for example, indicating existing or missing signage, location of the formation of lines/queues, and specific room

identification (such as the restroom) were within the context of environmental graphics. The Society of Environmental Graphic Designers (SEGD) identifies environmental graphic design as “many design disciplines including graphic, architectural, interior, landscape, and industrial design, all concerned with the visual aspects of wayfinding, communicating identity and information, and shaping the idea of place” (SEGD, 2010).

This study revealed that a major factor within this particular airport terminal was the identification of signage and wayfinding techniques. The participants indicated appropriate signage, but also inappropriate signage, such as a hand-written sign duct-taped to a wall. This may indicate that even though the layout for the airport terminal is specific; the wayfinding techniques may or may not be at the forefront of the traveler’s thinking process. For the frequent traveler, the wayfinding procedures might not be as much a priority as compared to those of an infrequent traveler, where the individual might be focused on the more procedural aspects of the airport. The question that would provide the most benefit to all parties involved would be how to make wayfinding strategies identifiable to everyone. These environmental elements are crucial for aiding in the circulation of space and space planning, which is a major function of interior design curriculums. Therefore, this study indicated that when attempting to anticipate what happens within a particular environment, the actual experience within the environment, and noting what did happen within the environment, a factor that was most frequently indicated by the participants of this study, who were senior interior design students, was the concept of signage and its role within the airport environment.

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